

A Cooperative Multi-UAV Framework for Bridge Inspection

Miguel Gil-Castilla, Alvaro Ramiro Poma, Alvaro Caballero, Anibal Ollero

Abstract—Bridges are vital infrastructure assets whose maintenance is essential to ensure safety and efficient traffic flow. However, due to their nature, they are often located in hard-to-reach places, which makes their regular inspection challenging and risky for human operators. This paper presents a comprehensive multi-UAV (Unmanned Aerial Vehicle) framework for fast and efficient cooperative bridge inspection, leveraging commercial UAVs with open-source tools and integrating both a custom Ground Control Station and advanced multi-UAV motion planning based on Signal Temporal Logic. The proposed approach enables autonomous and safe data collection while minimizing operational constraints and human intervention, making it a valuable contribution to UAV-based infrastructure monitoring. The presented framework has been validated in a real-world environment, showcasing its effectiveness in coordinating UAV teams for autonomous structural inspections.

I. INTRODUCTION

The inspection and maintenance of large-scale infrastructures, such as power lines, bridges, and roads, pose substantial challenges due to their hard-to-reach location, complexity, and the hazardous conditions often encountered. Traditional inspection methods, which typically rely on manual labor or manned aircraft, expose workers to significant risks, including operating at great heights, dealing with electrical hazards, navigating confined spaces, and working in structurally unstable areas. These methods are not only dangerous but also highly time-consuming, resource-intensive, and expensive, often requiring the temporary closure of services, such as road traffic, further adding to societal and economic disruptions.

Recent advancements in autonomous control, sensor technologies, communication systems, and artificial intelligence have accelerated the adoption of UAVs (Unmanned Aerial Vehicles) for industrial and civil applications. UAVs have emerged as a promising alternative to inspect and maintain large infrastructures, offering notable advantages over traditional approaches such as manned helicopters, elevated work platforms, or ground-based inspections [1]–[7]. By autonomously navigating complex environments and conducting routine inspections with minimal human intervention, UAVs enhance safety, efficiency, and cost-effectiveness.

For particularly large or intricate infrastructures, however, the use of a single UAV often falls short in meeting operational requirements. Deploying and coordinating multiple UAVs, eventually with complementary capabilities, can significantly improve inspection efficiency and coverage. Each

Miguel Gil-Castilla (e-mail: mgil18@us.es, corresponding author), Alvaro Ramiro Poma (e-mail: apoma@us.es), Alvaro Caballero (e-mail: alvarocaballero@us.es) and Anibal Ollero (e-mail: aollero@us.es) are with the GRVC Robotics Lab, University of Seville, Camino de los Descubrimientos S/N, 41092 Seville, Spain.

Fig. 1. Multi-UAV team performing fully-autonomous visual inspection of a real bridge located in Aznalcóllar (Spain).

UAV can focus on specific tasks aligned with its design and capabilities, enabling faster fault detection and more comprehensive data collection. To achieve this, it is essential to develop a robust, scalable, and flexible framework to manage multi-UAV missions, ensuring adaptability to dynamic environments and the ability to respond effectively to emergencies.

Several studies have explored UAVs for bridge inspection and maintenance. In [8], a vision-based control law enables quasi-stationary UAV flights using homography matrix computations for navigation. Another work [9] highlights the role of UAVs in simplifying bridge inspections, particularly for hard-to-reach structural components that traditionally require specialized equipment or trained personnel. Techniques like SLAM (Simultaneous Localization and Mapping) have also been proposed to enhance UAV navigation and mapping capabilities for more effective bridge inspections [10]. Imagery-based 3D reconstruction from UAVs has been explored as a safer, more cost-effective alternative for bridge inspection, with studies proposing workflows for data acquisition, reconstruction, quality evaluation, and damage detection, while also highlighting challenges in capturing fine structural details [11].

In the OMICRON project¹, the authors of this paper contributed to developing solutions for coordinating multiple inspection UAVs, enhancing the efficiency and coverage of road inspections while enabling high-resolution imagery and 3D mapping for integration into a digital twin. As part of this effort, bridge roadways were inspected in challenging, hard-

¹<https://omicronproject.eu/>

to-access locations, demonstrating the capability of a multi-UAV system to operate in complex environments where traditional inspection methods are limited.

In a multi-UAV context, ROS-MAGNA [12] provides a robust framework to plan and coordinate multi-UAV missions. Recent studies have moved from custom-built UAVs to modified commercial drones, such as in [13], where a DJI M300 quadrotor was integrated with a ROS-based algorithm for early forest fire detection.

This paper presents a cooperative multi-UAV approach designed to address the challenges of fast and efficient bridge inspection (see Figure 1). By leveraging a team of UAVs with complementary capabilities, the proposed method enables comprehensive autonomous inspection coverage while minimizing operational time and costs. With minimal human intervention, the approach incorporates advanced coordination strategies, real-time adaptability, and robust planning algorithms, ensuring seamless operation even in complex and dynamic environments.

The main contributions of this paper are threefold:

- 1) Comprehensive multi-UAV framework: a novel framework for the cooperative operation of multiple UAVs is proposed, integrating a custom Ground Control Station (GCS) and enabling efficient and adaptive performance during bridge inspections.
- 2) Advanced multi-UAV motion planning for bridge inspections: the paper introduces a motion planning method based on Signal Temporal Logic (STL) that optimizes UAV trajectories to ensure bridge coverage while maximizing safety and meeting other mission requirements.
- 3) Validation in real scenarios: the proposed approach is validated through realistic experiments, demonstrating its effectiveness in real-world bridge inspection scenarios.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows. Section II outlines the challenges and requirements specific to bridge inspection. Section III presents the aerial robots proposed for visual inspection tasks, highlighting their benefits and technological foundations. Section IV describes the management tools developed to facilitate multi-UAV coordination. Section V details the multi-UAV motion planning strategies formulated for the proposed framework. Validation results are presented and discussed in Section VI, and finally, Section VII concludes the paper with a summary of key findings and future research directions.

II. THE BRIDGE INSPECTION PROBLEM

Bridge inspection is a critical task in infrastructure maintenance, aiming to identify structural damage before it leads to safety hazards or expensive repairs. Traditional inspection methods, which involve human inspectors using booms, scaffolding, or manned aerial platforms, are time-consuming, costly, and disruptive to traffic. These methods are also limited by human subjectivity and restricted access to certain structural areas.

Recent advances in robotics and autonomous systems have introduced UAVs as a promising tool for bridge inspection. UAVs can access hazardous or confined areas and collect high-resolution imagery with minimal disruption. However, deploying UAVs for large-scale infrastructure inspection presents several challenges, including:

- Ensuring full visual coverage of complex 3D structures, particularly in GPS-denied or magnetically disturbed areas;
- Coordinating multiple UAVs efficiently to minimize overall inspection time and avoid redundant coverage;
- Managing UAV constraints such as battery limitations and the need for recharging;
- Integrating data collection seamlessly into maintenance workflows.

To address these challenges, this paper proposes a formalized and scalable approach to bridge inspection using a team of UAVs coordinated via a mission planning strategy encoded using STL. The inspection task is modeled as a composition of spatial-temporal requirements that capture both safety and operational constraints. These include maintaining UAVs within the allowed workspace, avoiding obstacles and restricted areas, ensuring safe inter-UAV distances, visiting all inspection targets for a specified duration, and returning to home positions upon task completion.

The mission specifications are encoded in an STL formula, allowing for systematic validation and generation of feasible, conflict-free trajectories that can be executed autonomously. This formal framework guarantees correct-by-design behaviors and enables complex inspection objectives to be handled by a multi-agent system. The proposed method is integrated into a custom GCS capable of supervising and visualizing the execution of coordinated multi-UAV inspection missions. The entire system is validated in a real-world scenario involving the inspection of a highway bridge, demonstrating the effectiveness of the approach in a realistic and operationally challenging environment.

III. AERIAL ROBOTS FOR VISUAL INSPECTION

For this research, we utilize two commercial DJI Matrice 210 V2 RTK UAVs, each equipped with specialized cameras: the Zenmuse Z30 for high-zoom imaging and the Zenmuse X5S to capture detailed, high-resolution visuals. This combination enables precise identification and documentation of defects such as cracks, corrosion, and surface wear, even in challenging inspection scenarios.

While commercial UAVs offer advanced hardware and reliable performance, their proprietary software often limits flexibility in research applications. To overcome this limitation, we modified the DJI platforms to integrate open-source tools, such as the Robot Operating System (ROS) [14].

The use of open-source tools not only provides greater control over the UAVs functionality but also facilitates integration with advanced planning and decision-making frameworks. This flexibility is essential to implement the proposed multi-UAV system, enabling coordinated missions, real-time adaptability to dynamic conditions, and efficient

data acquisition. By leveraging these modifications, the aerial robots serve as a versatile and powerful platform for advancing the state of the art in bridge inspection.

Figure 2 illustrates the hardware modifications required to run open-source software on our agents, depicting the back of the drone and detailing the accessible ports for properly connecting a third-party onboard computer and implementing the necessary integrations. The power output delivers a constant 2A current at 18V to 26V, supplying all connected electronics. The UART (serial port) is primarily used for autopilot telemetry, ensuring basic communication. Finally, a dual USB cable enables advanced sensing capabilities, such as camera streaming, visual perception, or target tracking.

Fig. 2. Hardware design and the connections between the modules of the DJI M210 V2 RTK specific hardware modification.

Regarding the software inside the UAV onboard computer, depicted in Figure 3, the primary ROS node is the DJI OSDK vehicle node², which manages the UAV state and movement by gathering data from onboard sensors. It also facilitates communication with the GCS through ROS, acting as a server that transmits telemetry data and provides basic control command services to the GCS client.

Building on top of the DJI OSDK, the mission handler serves as an abstraction layer, offering higher-level functionalities related to mission execution. In addition, a node was developed to enable efficient video streaming by utilizing the *ros_rtsp* package [15]. This setup allows the video feed from the DJI Zenmuse cameras, which is published as a ROS topic, to be converted into an RTSP stream. By creating an RTSP server, the GCS can access the live video feed, enhancing real-time situational awareness for the user during UAV operations and ensuring reliable monitoring of the inspection process.

The communication between the ground and aerial components is managed using the ROS *multimaster-fkie* tool [16]. This package allows each CPU to host its own ROS Master node, enabling sharing of services and topics over a common network. Importantly, once the mission begins, the ROS

nodes on the UAVs operate independently from the ground component, ensuring uninterrupted functionality even if the connection to the GCS is lost.

Meanwhile, the entire mission process, from upload to completion, is controlled by a Behavior Tree (BT) similarly to previous contribution [17], that ensures proper communication with the GCS, verifies mission uploads and commands, and monitors execution.

Finally, communication is a crucial component of the autonomous multi-UAV inspection system, enabling data and command transmission between the aerial and ground segments via a WiFi local network. The Ubiquiti Rocket Prism 5AC Gen 2 serves as the ground station, while the UAVs are equipped with Ubiquiti Bullet AC antennas, connected to their onboard computers via Ethernet. These devices provide reliable connectivity in both urban and rural environments, with a maximum range of approximately 4 km, ensuring effective mission execution.

IV. MULTI-UAV COORDINATION TOOL

The multi-UAV inspection of infrastructure in civil applications, such as bridge inspections, requires a robust and centralized control system to manage and coordinate UAV operations. This control system, which we have designated as the Management Tool, functions as a GCS application, serving as the primary platform for mission planning, real-time monitoring, and the management of images obtained during the mission. Building upon the work introduced in [18], the GCS has been enhanced in this paper to meet the specific demands of autonomous bridge inspection.

Figure 3 presents the updated system architecture, which incorporates mission logging through the integration of a database, as well as new interfaces to handle stored data. Additionally, a dedicated interface has been introduced to focus on individual UAV operations. The Management Tool allows operators to configure and upload missions, adjust parameters dynamically, and supervise multi-UAV operations through an intuitive interface. Furthermore, the system supports real-time video streaming, mission logging, and data storage for post-mission analysis.

A key feature of the GCS is its ability to automate the workflow to execute multi-UAV missions. This includes loading missions, commanding the UAVs, and automatically downloading mission data to the GCS once the UAVs complete their tasks. Throughout the entire process, operators can monitor mission progress in real time using intuitive interfaces. The GCS provides different views tailored to specific tasks: the main interface, which offers an overview of all UAVs and ongoing missions; the device detail interface, where operators can focus on an individual UAV, as shown in Figure 4; the mission planning interface, which interacts with the motion planner presented in Section V, and also enables route definition and parameter adjustments; and the mission execution interface, which allows real-time monitoring and interaction with UAVs. These interfaces ensure that operators can effectively oversee missions, respond to events, and

²https://github.com/dji-sdk/Onboard-SDK-ROS/blob/master/include/dji_osdk_ros/dji_vehicle_node.h

Fig. 3. Management Tool and GCS system architecture, illustrating all GCS components and interactions with UAV elements through several communication protocols.

interact with the drones when needed, providing an efficient inspection process.

Finally, the Management Tool provides a comprehensive data management framework, allowing UAVs to upload captured data, including visual imagery and thermal scans obtained from missions. Operators can then review mission results in an organized manner, facilitating an efficient decision-making process. These capabilities, combined with the modular enhancements introduced in this work, establish the GCS as a powerful tool for autonomous bridge inspection, reinforcing its role as an advanced management platform based on the system outlined in [18].

V. MULTI-UAV MOTION PLANNING

This section introduces a motion planning method specifically formulated to coordinate multi-UAV teams for the visual inspection of bridges, computing efficient UAV trajectories while ensuring safety. Inspired by previous contributions [19], [20], Robust STL has been adopted.

A. Preliminaries: Robust Signal Temporal Logic

STL was first-time introduced in [21] to monitor the behaviour of real-valued signals. Such logic allows the description of complex system behaviours in a succinct and unambiguous way, encoding requirements and specifications into a single STL formula φ . The full description of STL syntax and semantics can be found in [21], [22] and is not

Fig. 4. Management Tool: device detail interface for UAV_2, displaying all UAV attributes, live video streaming, telemetry, mission map, and distance sensor data for obstacle avoidance.

reported here for the sake of brevity. In short, an STL formula φ is defined over a set of predicates; these are, atomic propositions that yield simple operations, such as belonging to a region or comparisons with real values. These predicates are combined together using boolean (\neg , \wedge , \vee) and temporal (\diamond , \square , \mathcal{U}) operators, and the resulting STL formula φ is considered to be valid if the expression takes a true (\top) logic value, and invalid (\perp) otherwise.

The presence of system uncertainties, a dynamic environment, and unforeseen events can affect the satisfaction of an STL formula φ . In an attempt to have a manoeuvrability margin of satisfaction of φ , measuring how well (badly) a given specification is met, the concept of *robustness* ρ for the formula φ ; this is ρ_φ , can be formulated. This robustness can be leveraged to guide an optimization problem towards the best feasible solution to attain the mission satisfaction. Such value ρ relative to the system state \mathbf{x} at time instant t_k can be formally described by using the equations (1), where $t_k + \mathbf{I}$ is meant here as the Minkowski sum between the scalar t_k and the time interval \mathbf{I} , and $\mu_i(\mathbf{x}, t_k)$ represents the generic i -th predicate p_i evaluated at time t_k . Further details can be found in [21]–[23]. In this case, \mathbf{x} satisfies the STL formula φ at time t_k if $\rho_\varphi(\mathbf{x}, t_k) > 0$, and \mathbf{x} violates φ if $\rho_\varphi(\mathbf{x}, t_k) \leq 0$.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \rho_{p_i}(\mathbf{x}, t_k) &= \mu_i(\mathbf{x}, t_k) \\
 \rho_{\neg\varphi}(\mathbf{x}, t_k) &= -\rho_\varphi(\mathbf{x}, t_k) \\
 \rho_{\varphi_1 \wedge \varphi_2}(\mathbf{x}, t_k) &= \min(\rho_{\varphi_1}(\mathbf{x}, t_k), \rho_{\varphi_2}(\mathbf{x}, t_k)) \\
 \rho_{\square_1\varphi}(\mathbf{x}, t_k) &= \min_{t'_k \in [t_k + \mathbf{I}]} \rho_\varphi(\mathbf{x}, t'_k) \\
 \rho_{\diamond_1\varphi}(\mathbf{x}, t_k) &= \max_{t'_k \in [t_k + \mathbf{I}]} \rho_\varphi(\mathbf{x}, t'_k) \\
 \rho_{\varphi_1 \mathcal{U} \varphi_2}(\mathbf{x}, t_k) &= \max_{t'_k \in [t_k + \mathbf{I}]} \left(\min(\rho_{\varphi_2}(\mathbf{x}, t'_k)), \right. \\
 &\quad \left. \min_{t''_k \in [t_k, t'_k]} (\rho_{\varphi_1}(\mathbf{x}, t''_k)) \right)
 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

Thus, the control inputs \mathbf{u} can be computed by maximizing the robustness ρ over the set of finite-state and input sequences \mathbf{x} and \mathbf{u} , respectively. The obtained sequence \mathbf{u}^* associated with \mathbf{x}^* is valid if $\rho_\varphi(\mathbf{x}^*, t_k)$ is positive for every value of time

t_k , where \mathbf{x}^* and \mathbf{u}^* obey the dynamical system. The larger $\rho_\varphi(\mathbf{x}^*, t_k)$ is, the more robust the behavior of the system is.

B. STL Motion Planner

Starting from mission specifications encoded as an STL formula φ , the trajectory generation for multi-rotor UAVs can be formulated according to [24] as the set of three optimization problems, one for each j -axis ($j = \{1, 2, 3\}$) of the inertial reference frame:

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{maximize} \quad \rho_\varphi(p_k^{(j)}, v_k^{(j)}, t_k) \\ & p_k^{(j)}, v_k^{(j)}, a_k^{(j)} \\ & \text{s.t.} \quad |v_k^{(j)}| \leq v_{max}^{(j)}, |a_k^{(j)}| \leq a_{max}^{(j)} \\ & \mathbf{S}_k^{(j)}, \forall k = \{0, 1, \dots, N-1\} \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where $p_k^{(j)}$, $v_k^{(j)}$, and $a_k^{(j)}$ represent the positions, velocities, and accelerations of the UAVs at time instant t_k along the j -axis ($j = \{1, 2, 3\}$) of the inertial reference frame, $v_{max}^{(j)}$ and $a_{max}^{(j)}$ are the desired maximum values of velocity and acceleration along the motion, respectively, and $\mathbf{S}_k^{(j)}(p_k^{(j)}, v_k^{(j)}, a_k^{(j)}) = (p_{k+1}^{(j)}, v_{k+1}^{(j)}, a_{k+1}^{(j)})^\top$ are the motion primitives presented in [25]. For more information about STL motion planning for multi-rotor UAVs, a detailed description can be found in [24].

C. Mission Specifications for Bridge Inspection

The encoding of the mission specifications for bridge inspection into an STL formula φ is detailed hereinafter. From a motion planning perspective, bridge inspection tasks consist of a set of different requirements. Some of them are associated with safety and must be fulfilled during all the operation time t_N . These requirements include staying within the workspace (φ_{ws}), while avoiding both collisions with the obstacles there and flying inside restricted areas (φ_{obs}), and keeping safety distances between UAVs (φ_{dis}). Other requirements linked to the mission itself must be satisfied following a sequence or after certain events. In this sense, the team of UAVs must visit a set of inspection points once and stay there for the inspection time t_{ins} (φ_{ins}). Additionally, each UAV must return to the home position after completing the inspection task (φ_h). All these requirements can be encoded in the STL formula:

$$\varphi = \square_{t_N} (\varphi_{ws} \wedge \varphi_{obs} \wedge \varphi_{dis}) \bigwedge \diamond_{t_N} \varphi_{ins} \mathcal{U} \varphi_h \quad (3)$$

where $\wedge, \square, \diamond, \mathcal{U}$ are the operators *And*, *Always*, *Sometime* and *Until*, respectively, and:

$$\varphi_{ws} = \forall p_k^{(j)} \in (\underline{p}_{ws}^{(j)}, \bar{p}_{ws}^{(j)}) \quad (4a)$$

$$\varphi_{obs} = \forall_{\substack{\text{obstacle and} \\ \text{restricted area}}} p_k^{(j)} \notin (\underline{p}_{obs}^{(j)}, \bar{p}_{obs}^{(j)}) \quad (4b)$$

$$\varphi_{dis} = \forall_{\text{UAV } n \neq d} \sqrt{\sum_j \left(p_k^{(j)} - p_n^{(j)} \right)^2} > \Gamma \quad (4c)$$

$$\varphi_{ins} = \forall_{\substack{\text{inspection} \\ \text{points}}} \square_{t_{ins}} p_k^{(j)} \in (\underline{p}_{ins}^{(j)}, \bar{p}_{ins}^{(j)}) \quad (4d)$$

$$\varphi_h = \forall p_k^{(j)} \in (\underline{p}_h^{(j)}, \bar{p}_h^{(j)}) \quad (4e)$$

Equation (4a) imposes the position of the UAV d at time instant t_k along the j -axis ($j = \{1, 2, 3\}$) of the inertial reference frame; this is ${}^d p_k^{(j)}$, to stay within the boundaries of the workspace area, with $\underline{p}_{ws}^{(j)}$ and $\bar{p}_{ws}^{(j)}$ denoting its minimum and maximum values along the j -axis of the reference frame. Similarly, equations (4b), (4d) and (4e) set the obstacle and restricted area avoidance, inspection and mission completion specifications, respectively, where $\underline{p}_{obs}^{(j)}$, $\underline{p}_{ins}^{(j)}$, $\underline{p}_h^{(j)}$, $\bar{p}_{obs}^{(j)}$, $\bar{p}_{ins}^{(j)}$ and $\bar{p}_h^{(j)}$ are the vertex positions along the j -axis of the reference frame of bounding boxes delimiting the obstacles and restricted areas, the inspection points and the UAV home. Finally, equation (4c) is the safety distance requirement of the UAV d with respect to the rest of UAVs n ($n \neq d$), with the square-root term representing the distance $\gamma_{d,n}$ between the pair of UAVs $\{d, n\}$ and Γ being its minimum admissible value. It should be noted that the notation in the previous equations has been particularised for the single UAV d to make them more readable. However, the formulation can be extended to the complete team of UAVs with an appropriate set of operators and indices.

VI. VALIDATION

To assess the effectiveness of the multi-UAV inspection framework, a real-world validation was conducted on a complex and operational highway bridge. This section presents the case of the study, detailing the infrastructure characteristics and inspection methodology, followed by an analysis of the experimental results.

A. Use Case: Settefonti Bridge

The Settefonti Bridge, part of the Milan-Rome-Naples motorway and depicted in Figure 5, is a crucial infrastructure along the Bologna-Florence segment of the Autostrada del Sole, one of the most significant transportation routes in Italy. Located in the Apennine Mountains at approximately 700 meters above sea level, the bridge operates under active traffic conditions, requiring careful planning to ensure safety during inspection. Given the complexity of the structure and the presence of fast-moving vehicles, it was necessary to implement temporary traffic closures in specific areas to create a safe environment for both UAV operations and personnel on-site.

Structurally, the viaduct consists of two separate roadways with spans of varying lengths: seven bays on the southbound lane and six on the northbound lane, with spans measuring 13.8, 20.8, and up to 85 meters. The primary spans, 85 meters long, feature pre-stressed reinforced concrete beams (3 meters high, spaced 2.8 meters apart), stiffened by cross beams and a 15 cm slab. The bridge's piers incorporate multiple columns, with the main bays supported by 1.1 x 1.1 meter shafts, reinforced every 9 meters with cross beams. The viaduct has undergone several maintenance interventions, including anti-seismic reinforcements and concrete restoration near the supports³.

³Detailed structural information was obtained from the project website: <https://www.mapei.com/pr/es-us/proyectos/detalle-del-proyecto/viadotto-settefonti-1466>

By deploying multiple UAVs equipped with high-resolution cameras, we aimed to generate detailed imagery of the bridge, identifying potential structural issues and validating the efficiency of the proposed inspection framework. The following subsection presents the experimental results obtained from this deployment.

Fig. 5. Aerial view of the Settefonti Bridge in Italy, a critical highway viaduct and the test site for the UAV-based inspection experiments.

B. Experimental Results

The bridge inspection was conducted by deploying the GCS in a field near the bridge, along with two DJI Matrice M210 UAVs. The UAVs communicated directly with the GCS using Vehicle-to-Ground (V2G) communication, as illustrated in Figure 6.

Fig. 6. Setup of the multi-UAV bridge inspection, showing the UAVs used, the GCS, and its components.

The GCS consisted of a ground-based computer running the Management Tool, ensuring stable communication with the UAV fleet throughout the inspection process. A Ubiquiti Prism AC radio was used to establish a reliable connection with the UAVs. Additionally, two DJI D-RTK 2 mobile stations were deployed to enhance the UAVs' positioning accuracy during the inspection.

To demonstrate the motion planning capabilities, Figure 7 presents the computed trajectories for the multi-UAV team assigned to the complete bridge deck inspection. Inspection points were evenly distributed along both sides of the bridge deck at two different heights: one for inspecting the lateral side and the other for road coverage (i.e., the top part of the bridge deck). To ensure road traffic safety, flying over the roads was strictly prohibited, which was enforced by defining restricted areas over them. As a result, one of the UAVs had to cross the road by flying over the tunnel located on the right side of the figure. The results indicate that the motion planner

successfully computes efficient trajectories while ensuring safety among UAVs, road traffic, and the environment, as collisions with both the ground and the bridge are effectively avoided.

Fig. 7. UAV trajectories planned for the visual inspection of the complete Settefonti bridge deck.

In spite of previous planning results, given the operational constraints of an active highway and legal restrictions prohibiting flights directly over the bridge, the real inspection was conducted in a controlled and simplified manner to prioritize safety while minimizing traffic disruptions. The mission focused on the external face of the structure closest to the GCS, ensuring compliance with regulations while still capturing critical visual data. The inspection was carried out autonomously using the two UAVs with precomputed flight plans. UAV 1 was assigned to inspect the longest pile, following a set of inspection points vertically located and evenly distributed for comprehensive coverage, while UAV 2 focused on inspecting the entire lateral face of the bridge deck, capturing detailed structural imagery along its length. These flight plans were computed by the multi-UAV motion planner and then loaded into the Management Tool (see Figure 8) before commanding their autonomous execution. This approach enabled a thorough structural assessment, reduced the need for extended road closures, and maintained efficient traffic flow.

Figure 9 shows the Matrice M210 UAV performing the autonomous deck inspection. This UAV was equipped with a high-resolution camera, enabling both real-time and detailed post-mission analysis of structural imperfections. As illustrated in Figure 10, significant defects with concrete spalling exposed the reinforcement bars, highlighting critical areas of concern. This capability allows human operators to quickly identify structural weaknesses, improving the efficiency and accuracy of bridge inspections.

VII. CONCLUSIONS

This work successfully demonstrated a comprehensive multi-UAV inspection approach for fast and efficient bridge assessment, leveraging commercial UAVs with open source tools and integrating both an advanced planning method and a robust GCS. The proposed system was validated in a real-world environment, showcasing its effectiveness in coordinating UAVs for autonomous structural in-

Fig. 8. Multi-UAV bridge inspection mission at the Settefonti Bridge (Italy). The figure illustrates the GCS interface during the inspection, showcasing real-time monitoring of two DJI Matrice 210 quadrotors (uav_1 and uav_2) and an external UAV (uav_100) flying at different heights. The selected UAV live video stream is also displayed, providing a detailed view of the inspection process.

Fig. 9. UAV_2 conducting the visual inspection of the lateral face of the bridge deck. The top image shows a ground-level view during the operation, while the bottom image provides the UAV aerial perspective, highlighting the UAV position relative to the structure.

specifications. The methodology ensures efficient data collection while minimizing operational constraints, making it a valuable contribution to UAV-based infrastructure monitoring. The code for this work is openly accessible on GitHub at https://github.com/alvcaballero/multiUAV_system under the MIT license.

Future work will focus on enhancing the system with automatic real-time fault detection and emergency management capabilities. Additionally, improvements in vision-based localization relative to the inspection asset will address challenges such as GNSS (Global Navigation Satellite System) losses when operating under the bridge or magnetometer interference caused by the structure's metal components. These advancements will further increase the system reliability and autonomy in complex inspection scenarios.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work has been supported by the European Projects AEROSUB and TEMA, funded by the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme of the European Commission under grant agreements No 101189723 and 101093003, respectively. This work has also been partially supported by the 2023 FPI Program of the Spanish Ministerio de Ciencia, Innovación y Universidades in the subprogram Subprograma Estatal de Formación del Programa Estatal para Desarrollar, Atraer y Retener Talento, en el marco del Plan Estatal de Investigación Científica, Técnica y de Innovación 2021-2023.

Fig. 10. Some defects identified during the autonomous inspection: structural deterioration, corrosion, concrete loss and water infiltration (top) and a significant crack with concrete spalling exposing the reinforcement bars, which indicates potential corrosion and water infiltration issues (bottom).

The authors would like to thank José Luis Andrade for his role as coordinator during the execution of the experiments presented in this paper.

REFERENCES

- [1] R. Tapia, J. R. Martínez-de Dios, and A. Ollero, "Efficient Mosaicking for Linear Infrastructure Inspection using Aerial Robots," in *2019 Jornadas de Automática*, 2019, pp. 802–809.
- [2] A. Caballero, R. Tapia, and A. Ollero, "Combining route planning and visual servoing for offshore wind-turbine inspection using UAVs," *Iberian Robotics Conference*, 2024.
- [3] A. Ollero, G. Heredia, A. Franchi, G. Antonelli, K. Kondak, A. Sanfeliu, A. Viguria, J. R. Martínez-de Dios, F. Pierrri, J. Cortes, A. Santamaria-Navarro, M. A. Trujillo Soto, R. Balachandran, J. Andrade-Cetto, and A. Rodríguez, "The AEROARMS Project: Aerial Robots with Advanced Manipulation Capabilities for Inspection and Maintenance," *IEEE Robotics & Automation Magazine*, vol. 25, no. 4, pp. 12–23, 2018.
- [4] M. A. Trujillo, J. R. Martínez-de Dios, C. Martín, A. Viguria, and A. Ollero, "Novel Aerial Manipulator for Accurate and Robust Industrial NDT Contact Inspection: A New Tool for the Oil and Gas Inspection Industry," *Sensors*, vol. 19, no. 6, 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://www.mdpi.com/1424-8220/19/6/1305>
- [5] P. J. Sanchez-Cuevas, P. Ramon-Soria, B. Arrue, A. Ollero, and G. Heredia, "Robotic System for Inspection by Contact of Bridge Beams Using UAVs," *Sensors*, vol. 19, no. 2, 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://www.mdpi.com/1424-8220/19/2/305>
- [6] Z. Fang and A. V. Savkin, "Strategies for Optimized UAV Surveillance in Various Tasks and Scenarios: A Review," *Drones*, vol. 8, no. 5, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.mdpi.com/2504-446X/8/5/193>
- [7] I. Feitosa, B. Santos, and P. G. Almeida, "Pavement Inspection in Transport Infrastructures Using Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs)," *Sustainability*, vol. 16, no. 5, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.mdpi.com/2071-1050/16/5/2207>
- [8] N. Metni and T. Hamel, "A UAV for bridge inspection: Visual servoing control law with orientation limits," *Automation in construction*, vol. 17, no. 1, pp. 3–10, 2007.
- [9] N. Hallermann and G. Morgenthal, "Visual inspection strategies for large bridges using Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAV)," in *Proc. of 7th IABMAS, International Conference on Bridge Maintenance, Safety and Management*, 2014, pp. 661–667.
- [10] B. Chan, H. Guan, J. Jo, and M. Blumenstein, "Towards UAV-based bridge inspection systems: A review and an application perspective," *Structural Monitoring and Maintenance*, vol. 2, no. 3, pp. 283–300, 2015.
- [11] S. Chen, D. F. Laefer, E. Mangina, S. I. Zolanvari, and J. Byrne, "UAV bridge inspection through evaluated 3D reconstructions," *Journal of Bridge Engineering*, vol. 24, no. 4, p. 05019001, 2019.
- [12] J. A. Millan-Romera, H. Perez-Leon, A. Castillejo-Calle, I. Maza, and A. Ollero, "ROS-MAGNA, a ROS-based framework for the definition and management of multi-UAS cooperative missions," in *2019 International Conference on Unmanned Aircraft Systems (ICUAS)*, 2019, pp. 1477–1486.
- [13] S. Li, L. Qiao, Y. Zhang, and J. Yan, "An Early Forest Fire Detection System Based on DJI M300 Drone and H20T Camera," in *2022 International Conference on Unmanned Aircraft Systems (ICUAS)*, 2022, pp. 932–937.
- [14] M. Quigley, K. Conley, B. P. Gerkey, J. Faust, T. Foote, J. Leibs, R. Wheeler, and A. Y. Ng, "ROS: an open-source Robot Operating System," in *ICRA Workshop on Open Source Software*, 2009.
- [15] "ros_rstp - ROS package to subscribe to an ROS Image topic and serve it up as a RTSP video feed with different mount points," 2025, https://github.com/CircusMonkey/ros_rstp, Last accessed on 2025-02-07.
- [16] "Multimaster fkie - The metapackage to combine the nodes required to establish and manage a multimaster network," 2024, <https://github.com/fkie/multimaster.fkie>, Last accessed on 2025-02-07.
- [17] M. Gil-Castilla, R. Tapia, I. Maza, and A. Ollero, "Modular Framework for Autonomous Waypoint Following and Landing Based on Behavior Trees," in *2024 7th Iberian Robotics Conference (ROBOT)*, 2024, pp. 1–6.
- [18] A. R. Poma, A. Caballero, I. Maza, and A. Ollero, "Open-Source Web-Based Ground Control Station for Long-Range Inspection with Multiple UAV s," in *2024 International Conference on Unmanned Aircraft Systems (ICUAS)*. IEEE, 2024, pp. 1385–1392.
- [19] A. Caballero and G. Silano, "A signal temporal logic motion planner for bird diverter installation tasks with multi-robot aerial systems," *IEEE Access*, 2023.
- [20] G. Silano, A. Caballero, D. Liuzza, L. Iannelli, S. Bogdan, and M. Saska, "A Signal Temporal Logic approach for task-based coordination of multi-aerial systems: A wind turbine inspection case study," *Robotics and Autonomous Systems*, vol. 186, p. 104905, 2025.
- [21] O. Maler and D. Nickovic, "Monitoring temporal properties of continuous signals," in *Formal Techniques, Modelling and Analysis of Timed and Fault-Tolerant Systems*. Springer, 2004, pp. 152–166.
- [22] A. Donzé and O. Maler, "Robust satisfaction of temporal logic over real-valued signals," in *International Conference on Formal Modeling and Analysis of Timed Systems*. Springer, 2010, pp. 92–106.
- [23] G. Pola and M. D. Di Benedetto, "Control of Cyber-Physical-Systems with logic specifications: A formal methods approach," *Annual Reviews in Control*, vol. 47, pp. 178–192, 2019.
- [24] G. Silano, T. Baca, R. Penicka, D. Liuzza, and M. Saska, "Power Line Inspection Tasks With Multi-Aerial Robot Systems Via Signal Temporal Logic Specifications," *IEEE Robotics and Automation Letters*, vol. 6, no. 2, pp. 4169–4176, 2021.
- [25] M. W. Mueller, M. Hehn, and R. D'Andrea, "A Computationally Efficient Motion Primitive for Quadcopter Trajectory Generation," *IEEE Transactions on Robotics*, vol. 31, no. 6, pp. 1294–1310, 2015.